

POLICY BRIEF

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SMART TOURISM CITIES AND THE OPTIMIZATION OF SDGS – AGENDA 2030 Author: Luzia Costa Becker

POLICY STATEMENT

Five years after their approval by the United Nations, the Sustainable Development Goals – SDG – have become an important source of debate and mobilization in the proposition of public policies in several countries, including Brazil. By 2030, a new civilizational consensus on meaningful issues of human life shall be built, from the eradication of poverty to the development of smart cities and the protection of the oceans. In this process, tourism, which accounts for 10,3% of the world's GDP and employment (1), due to its relevance in the global economic panorama, stands as an essential tool for the fulfillment of the 17 SDGs. Since Brazil ranks second in natural resources and ninth in cultural resources, revealing an impressive potential for developing tourism on a sustainable basis (2), the great challenge is to change municipalities with this potential into a smart tourist destination.

BACKGROUND

In the history of the tourism policy in Brazil, from the first regulations of the sector in the different entities of the federal public administration, in the mid-1930s, to the drafting of the first National Tourism Plan (PLANTUR: 1992) followed by the National Plan for Tourism Municipalization (PNMT: 1994), the National Tourism Policy (PNT: 1996) and the Tourism Regionalization Program: Brazil's Itineraries (*Roteiros do Brasil* - 2004), the goal of the federal government remains the same: to promote the generation of employment and income and the development of municipalities and peripheral regions of the country (3). A process that ranges from nation development action to regional and municipal practice of the sustainable tourism development. From an **economic** point of view, the sustainable tourism policy requires that the generation of wealth through the activity in the locality also generates social equity. From an **environmental** point of view, that the exploitation of natural resources through the activity generates ecological caution. From a **cultural** point of view, that the exploitation of the material and immaterial heritage of the locality generates inclusion and incorporation of the populations that inhabit the tourist destination. Finally, from a **political** point of view, that the engagement of the citizens in the activity generates sharing of public management. Under the normative principles of sustainability, the National Tourism Plan 2018-2022 has defined global goals for tourism in the country. Concerning the quantitative aspect, these goals aim to increase the number of foreign tourists and the revenue produced by them, also to increase the number of Brazilians traveling in the country and the number of jobs generated by tourism. It also has guidelines with qualitative aspects as strengthening the regionalization of tourism; improving quality and competitiveness; encouraging innovation; and promoting sustainability.

FINDINGS

Data from IBGE indicate that tourism directly contributes for about 3.7% of the national GDP and 3% of the total of employments in the country. In international tourism, Brazil went from a level of 4.1 million international tourist arrivals in 2003, to a result of more than 6 million in recent years. Nevertheless, Brazil is not a major international tourist destination, with less than 6 million tourists a year. In contrast, national tourism is highly active, 59 million tourists and 190 million travels, due to a national market of 200 million inhabitants, the improvements in living standards, and the consequent increase in tourism spending over the last few decades. This helped build a powerful and reasonably structured tourism sector (4).

However, the several public and private initiatives, government programs, and National Tourism Plans carried out in the country with the purpose of stimulating the sector's competitiveness, and even the organization of major events, such as the Confederations Cup (2013), the FIFA World Cup (2014), and the Olympics and Paralympics (2016), according to Sousa (2018), have not effectively achieved the proposed goals. Brazil's tourism balance has been invariably negative in recent years. Revenues ranged from \$1.8 billion in 2000 to \$6.0 billion in 2016, and the variation in expenses was from \$3.8 billion to \$8.4 billion over the same period.

This situation was aggravated by the economic and social crisis, caused by the possibility of contagion from Covid-19. In addition to the suspension of travel and the closing of borders around the globe, the industry chain has been affected because even local residents cannot go to recreational areas because of the risk of contagion, since tourist sites are by their nature crowded places (5). Even with the end of the period of major social isolation, the willingness to spend on travel will be conditioned to a greater confidence in the health safety of the destination to be visited as a competitive differential.

The lack of structuring of the tourism sector was pointed out by several authors as a cause of its low competitiveness. In the tourism industry – which accounts only for economic phenomena, such as GDP growth – the state acts without taking into consideration the qualitative historic-cultural processes, ethical approaches, and even the environmental impacts of the activity (6).

According to the 2017 Report of the Civil Society Working Group for the 2030 Agenda, we are moving in the opposite direction of what was expected to be achieved with the implementation of the goals of the 17 SDGs in the country. According to the 2020 Report, there have been setbacks in all areas with the arrival of the Covid-19 pandemic in Brazil. In the case of tourism, SDGs 8, 12 and 14, specifically, the target 12.b. focused on the development of tools to monitor the impacts of sustainable tourism development that creates jobs, promotes culture and local products, it is indicated that the Plan for Sustainable Tourism, combined with the Plan for Production and Consumption, is halt.

CONCLUSIONS

It is thus concluded that the conventional strategies for promoting the tourist destination have become obsolete and, although the national tourism sector has advanced, there are challenges related to the impact of the Information and Communication Technologies – ICTs, new patterns of demand behavior, new business model, greater socio-environmental sensibility, among others. In this regard, the scenario of structural changes in tourism coincides with the interest in transforming the traditional tourism model, creating general lines of action that serves guidelines for destination managers to take the step of turning tourist cities into tourist cities in Smart Tourism Destinations – STD, that is, those destinations whose new management approaches will guarantee the environmental quality and sustainability of destinations; the improvement and differentiation of tourist experiences offered; the use of ICTs for the supply of tourism products and services; the improvement of communication of the territory's attractions; and the discovery of new forms of competitiveness in the current tourism scenario.

SUGGESTIONS

According to the KPMG's report, there is a global trend for cities to rethink their value proposition, since the reinvention, in the context of the possibilities posed by digital technologies, produces quite different expectations (7).

In the case of Brazil, most of its 5,570 municipalities have not yet reached the status of strategic digital city, that is, they have not applied information technology resources in the management of the city and in making public information and services available to citizens. The Electronic Government Program, created in October 2000 to develop actions to improve the provision of public services offered by the Internet, shall, therefore, be optimized.

Smart, digitally-enabled cities play an important role, helping government evolve the urban environment in order to deliver a better, cleaner and more efficient quality of life for its citizens. SDG 11 on sustainable cities and communities might promote the improvement of urban infrastructure and accessibility, the regeneration of public spaces, and the preservation of cultural and natural heritage, assets on which tourism activity depends. Investment in green infrastructure (more efficient transportation, reduced air pollution) will result in smarter and greener cities for residents and tourists.

Coinciding or not with the geographic boundaries of the smart city, the reinvention of the city as SDT, besides innovation and technologies, shall also include elements such as sustainability, governance, accessibility, and the residents. In this context, post COVID-19 measures shall be taken and incorporated into the process of creating and/or reinventing the city as SDT (8).

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